

ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND CULTURE ON PERFORMANCE MEDIATED BY WORK ENGAGEMENT AND AGE MODERATION FOR HEALTH WORKERS

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Abstract

This research was conducted with the aim of examining and determining the influence of organizational support and culture on work engagement and performance as well as to analyze the mediating role of work engagement and moderation of age. This study used a correlational method design with a population comprising all health workers at the Kendari City Public Health Center, where the total sample used was 154 health workers. Data were collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using SEM-PLS Ver. 3. The findings of this research reveal that organizational support can significantly influence the increase in work engagement and performance of health workers as well as organizational culture. Work engagement plays a significant role in performance and partially mediates the influence of organizational support and culture on performance. Finally, the moderation test revealed that optimizing the provision of organizational support to younger health workers increased their work engagement. These findings contribute positively to understanding the role of organizations in encouraging individuals to work and improve their performance. In addition, these findings also increase the understanding of the relationship between organizational support provided to younger individuals and increasing their work engagement.

Keywords: Age, Organizational Support, Organizational Culture, Performance, Work Engagement.

INTRODUCTION

The provision of health services at Public Health Centers has dynamic characteristics and organizations. Various types of health workers with various scientific tools interact with one another. Current science and technology continue to develop rapidly, which health workers need to follow to provide quality services and produce performance that meets the goals of health services. The current changing conditions require the readiness of health workers to have superior characteristics and competencies, be creative, and innovate to maximize goals in providing health services. Human resources in the scope of existing health services cannot be separated from the effectiveness of the services provided because their existence is the most important determining aspect in the success of the vision and mission that has been set so that in realizing the vision and mission, an organization must be able to adapt its human resources to the existing environment. dynamic. The abilities and talents possessed by each individual provide different results, so success in creating optimal health development depends on the performance of each individual health worker (Rohman et al., 2021). Performance is a measurable action, behavior, and employee work result that contributes to achieving organizational goals (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000:216). The performance of health workers can be observed in the actions they take in carrying out tasks assigned by their agency.

To improve performance, Meyers et al. (2019) revealed that organizational members need to receive support from the organization as a manifestation of its appreciation for

themselves. In government bureaucracy, civil servants and non-civil servants are required to perform well in achieving optimal reform. High performance will be balanced with organizational support in carrying out its role of responsibility within the scope of work, but in practice, the organizational support provided is not only in the form of support that has been determined, but also needs to be supported by appreciation in the form of verbal remarks given by superiors to their members in quite difficult situations. Organizations provide a form of support in the hope that individuals within the organization can have superior skills at work and improve the balance of goals between the individual and the organization (Prabu and Wijayati, 2016). Meyers et al. (2019) stated that organizational support can create a feeling of joy and comfort for employees to carry out their duties and responsibilities well, which ultimately leads to the creation of appropriate work results. In addition, Gemilang and Riana (2021) and Silva and Lopes (2021) also state that organizational support has a positive influence on employees' performance. Apart from influencing the resulting performance, organizational support can also influence organizational members' work engagement. Based on Social Exchange Theory, it is stated that if someone gets help or support from an organization, that person will provide the same thing in the future. This is related to how the organization provides appropriate support to its employees. In line with this theory, existing employees will be happier and deeply involved in carrying out their work.

In good human resource management to improve performance, organizations need to pay attention to how the existing organizational culture guides the creation of values and norms as well as the behavior of organizational members within it. Organizational culture is a source of strength and inspiration for an organization; by creating a strong culture, an organization can increase its effectiveness in achieving its goals. An organization with a strong culture produces good long-term performance. Angeline et al (2023) in their research revealed that the better the organizational culture implemented in an organization, the better the work results or performance they produce. Abdullahi, Raman, and Solarin (2021) and Michulek et al. (2023) also revealed that organizational culture is a key factor in efforts to achieve good performance. Based on this, good organizational support provided and the organizational culture created within the organization can not only encourage the achievement of expected work results but can also create strong work involvement from employees towards their work units. Work engagement is an individual's sense of attachment to their work, so that when they work, they will be more enthusiastic about doing their work. Individuals who feel that they are involved in their work unit have a deep understanding of their work environment and work diligently to improve their performance (Juyumaya, 2022). The findings of Meyers et al. (2019), Park et al. (2020), and Bhardwaj and Kalia (2020) reveal that work engagement that is owned and felt by employees can encourage them to create work results that are satisfying and in line with organizational goals.

Considering the important aspect of health workers engaging in work, organizations also need to consider the age of existing health workers. Older health workers have high levels of work engagement. Robbins (2005) revealed that the older an employee in an organization, the higher the level of work involvement. Age plays an important role where organizations need to consider this so that efforts to provide organizational support can be achieved. Organizations need to pay attention to young employees who are still productive by providing better organizational support to ensure high work

engagement. In the age grouping based on Generation Theory, the current age group that has entered the world of work as a whole is Generation X and Generation Y, which are generations who have experienced and feel a workforce. To strive to create work engagement, an organization needs to look at which aspects an employee needs to receive stronger support to produce work engagement, and which aspects the organization needs to maintain existing support.

This explanation illustrates the importance of an organization providing support to its members and the need to apply values and norms as a culture that directs a person at work to produce deep work involvement and provide optimal performance. The Kendari City Public Health Center, as one of the government agencies providing health services to the community at the first level, needs to emphasize this to achieve more optimal services. Therefore, the aim of this research was to evaluate the impact of the organizational support provided and the organizational culture that exists at the Kendari City Public Health Center on improving the performance provided by health workers, as well as to examine the role of work engagement that is created to maximize the role of the organization in work success. In addition, this study also aims to reveal the role of strengthening organizational support for health workers at a younger age in optimizing their work engagement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

Performance is formally defined as the value of a series of employee behaviors that contribute, both positively and negatively, to the achievement of organizational goals (Colquitt *et al.*, 2018). This definition of performance includes behaviors that are within employees' control, but it places boundaries around which behaviors are (and are not) relevant to job performance. Performance is the extent to which an employee contributes to organizational effectiveness, with expectations related to his work role (Zablah *et al.*, 2012:25). According to Bernardin and Russell (1998), performance is a recording of the impact on specific work functions or activities during a certain period of time. Wood *et al.* (2011) revealed that performance is a concise measure of the quality and quantity of contributions of tasks carried out by individuals or groups for work units or organizations. Gibson *et al.* (2012) also stated that performance is the level of success in carrying out tasks and the ability to achieve predetermined goals. Performance is the achievement of work results achieved by employees based on predetermined standards and assessment measures (Mathis and Jackson, 2011).

Performance is considered not only as the scope of work itself but also as a more complex concept that includes a variety of behaviors directed at internal employees and external customers (Korschun *et al.*, 2014; Welbourne *et al.*, 1998). Therefore, to understand employee performance, attention must be paid to the different roles of employees in an organization. Scholars argue that role-based performance theory has served as a means to address this problem (Griffin *et al.*, 2007; Welbourne *et al.*, 1998) and have put forward a definition of job performance as a behavior-based skill that employees use to fulfill different aspects of their work roles that contribute either directly or indirectly to organizational goals (Borman and Motowidlo, 1993; Campbell, 1990; Welbourne *et al.*, 1998).

Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support is a theory in the behavioral literature. This theory explains the role of organizational members' perceptions of organizational relationships. An organization's relationship with employees shapes their attitudes and behaviors in the organization. Organizational support, often known as perceived organizational support, is an important concept in the organizational behavior literature, where organizational support can explain the relationship between organizational treatment, employee attitudes, and behavior towards their work and organization. The treatment carried out by the organization is used as a stimulus captured by employees, which is interpreted as a perception of the organization's support (Eisenberger *et al.*, 1986). Perceived organizational support is a form of support that convinces someone that the organization where they work values their contributions and cares about welfare (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002).

Organizational support is a contribution made by individuals who receive attention and concern from the organization regarding welfare. This concept means that they believe that the organization will provide proper attention and welfare in accordance with the performance contribution made (Eisenberger *et al.*, 1986). Robbins (2005) stated that organizational support is the degree to which individuals have confidence that the organization values their contributions and cares about welfare. Organizational support refers to employees' perception that the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being (Neves & Eisenberger, 2014). When employees perceive that their work is valued and cared for by the organization, it encourages them to incorporate membership as members of the organization into their self-identity. Essentially, the organizational support provided to employees shows the organization's commitment to employees. Employees reciprocate this support to improve their performance when doing work. Organizational support in the form of compensation, promotions, training, and safety at work is perceived by employees as a sign of the organization's concern for employee welfare.

Organizational Culture

In general, organizational culture is a pattern of basic assumptions, norms, and artifacts owned by organizational members. This represents the shared and taken-for-granted assumptions that make a person aware of how work should be done and evaluated and how employees relate to each other in a significant way (Cummings & Worley, 1993). The concept of organizational culture is manifested through how work is carried out and assessed in an organization. This also involves the interconnectedness of employee relationships both internally and externally to the organization. Organizational culture can also be seen through the form of relationships among workers within the organization as well as relationships with other related parties such as clients or customers (Ernawan, 2011). Organizational culture can be interpreted as an organization's personality, in which the existing culture can influence the overall activities of organizational members regarding how they work, how they view their work, how they work with colleagues, and how they see the future (Gibson *et al.*, 1994). At the organizational level, according to Meschi and Roger (1995), culture is a series of beliefs, assumptions, values, and perceptions of organizational members that influence and shape the attitudes and behavior of the group concerned.

Robbins (2005) explains that organizational culture is a system of meaning shared by each member of an organization which can differentiate the organization from others. Organizational culture influences behavior, value systems, shared beliefs, ways of interacting with organizational members, and structures and monitoring systems to produce norms and behaviors (Kast & Rosenzweig, 1995). Organizational culture has been maintained from generation to generation since the organization was founded, and is heavily influenced by predecessors who always try to pass it on to new members. Culture usually comes from several people, but more often, it comes from only one founder of the organization. This person develops a strategy according to the business environment they manage, which will ultimately become a culture (Kotter and Haskett, 1992).

Work Engagement

Work engagement is a concept in which employees have a sense of engagement; in other words, they feel attached to their work so that they are more enthusiastic about doing it. Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) defined work engagement as something positive that is related to behavior at work, which includes thoughts about the relationship between workers or employees and their work, which is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. In other words, employees who have high work engagement channel all their thoughts and energy towards their work and are more enthusiastic about working. Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) explain work engagement through the Job Demand-Resource theory (JD-R model); work engagement is influenced by two factors: job demand and job resources. Job demands are physical, psychological, and social factors that require physical, cognitive, and emotional effort, which can influence a person's level of work engagement through workload, and increasing workload can reduce employee work engagement. This is different from job resources, which can reduce workload and increase work engagement.

Work engagement refers to employees' involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm at work. Work engagement has developed from various concepts, including motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Saks, 2006). According to Kahn (1990), work engagement is conceptualized as organizational members carrying out their work roles, working, and expressing themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during work. Employee engagement is necessary to encourage employee morale. Brown and Trevino (2006) provide a definition of work engagement, namely where an employee is said to have work engagement in his work if the employee can identify himself psychologically with his work, and considers his performance important for himself, apart from the organization. Employees with high work engagement strongly identify with the type of work they do and really care about that type of work.

Age

Age is a unit of time that measures the time an object or creature exists, whether alive or dead. One factor that influences individual productivity is age. People who are still in their productive age usually have a higher level of productivity than older workers, so their physical abilities become weak and limited. Age is one of the strategic issues in managing human resources, especially when it is related to the work results of individuals or organizations within a wider scope. Over the last decade, there has been a belief that productivity is inversely related to age. Performance declines with age.

Robbins (2005:46) states that age is the length of time lived or existed (since birth or birth). The older an employee is, the higher their attachment to the organization

because the individual's opportunities to get another job become more limited as age increases. According to Yasin and Priyono (2016), the age of the workforce is the productive age of each individual. Productive age when each individual is able to provide services to other individuals. Productive age, in which every individual is able to provide a relationship between age and work, is an important issue that is increasingly being discussed. There are three reasons underlying this statement. First, there is the belief that productivity decreases with increasing age. Second, there is an increasing number of older workers, and third, regulations in a country for various purposes generally regulate the retirement age limit.

Figure 1: Research Model

Hypothesis

Organizational support on work engagement

Scaufeli and Baker (2004) revealed that organizational support in the workplace has the potential to encourage employees to work, thereby increasing their engagement. Good organizational support given to employees will encourage them to work well, which will further increase their involvement in their work. Meyers *et al.* (2019) found that organizational support has a positive and significant influence on work engagement. Park *et al.* (2020) also found that work engagement can be created in employees when there is positive support from the organization to carry out their duties well. Findings from Xu *et al.* (2021), Susita *et al.* (2021), Gemilang and Riana (2021), and Tian *et al.* (2023) also reveal that organizational support has a positive and significant influence on work engagement. Thus, the hypotheses in this study can be formulated as follows:

H1: Organizational support has a positive and significant effect on work engagement

Organizational support on Performance

Organizational support is the level at which employees feel that their welfare is well cared for by the company, so it can be said that employees who feel that their contributions are cared for and appreciated by the company will show their best performance by working hard to realize the company's goals and mission. Park *et al.*

(2020) in their research revealed that organizational support is able to have a positive impact on the resulting performance. Sanlioz, Sagbas, and Surucu (2022) also stated that good organizational support perceived by employees will lead to positive work behavior, ultimately creating optimal performance. Susita *et al.* (2021) also found that organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Other findings from Silva and Lopes (2021), Sanlioz, Sagbas, and Surucu (2022), and Karaalioglu and Karabulut (2019) also state that the perception of strong organizational support for employees will encourage them to work and create better performance. Good. Based on this, the hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H2: Organizational support has a positive and significant effect on performance

Organizational culture on work engagement

According to Social Exchange Theory, employees who are given organizational culture in the form of values through empowerment and training will feel a sense of consideration and repay the organization with deep involvement. Findings from Angeline *et al.* (2023) reveal that an organizational culture that is in line with organizational members will lead to high engagement behavior. Abdullahi, Raman, and Solarin (2021) in their research also concluded that work engagement can be created by a good culture within an organization. Conformity between existing values, norms, and behavior makes employees want to work better in the organization. Findings from Michulek *et al.* (2023) and Makhmut, Armanu, & Kurniawati (2023) also reveal that organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on work engagement. Based on this, the hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H3: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work engagement

Organizational culture on performance

A strong organizational culture can shape and improve performance (Robbins 2005:189). Angeline *et al.*, (2023) research findings reveal that organizational culture has an important role in shaping the performance of organizational members, where organizational culture determines how they work and carry out their daily activities. A good organizational culture leads to good organizational operations and ultimately improves the performance of existing organizational members. Fidyah and Setiawati (2019) in their research concluded that a good organizational culture has an impact on employee performance. Abdullahi, Raman, and Solarin (2021) also revealed that the better the organizational culture is accepted and felt by employees, the more performance they provide will also increase. Michulek *et al.* (2023) also reveal that organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on performance. Rohman *et al.* (2021) and Makhmut *et al.* (2023) also find that organizational culture plays an important role in improving organizational members' performance. Based on this, the hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H4: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on performance

Work engagement on performance

Employees who have strong ties are enthusiastic and proud of their work at the company and will increase their work role for the company's success, as demonstrated by the quality and quantity produced. Employees tied to their work and the company

will show their best performance for the company's success. Meyers *et al.* (2019) stated in their research that work engagement has a positive and significant influence on performance. Bhardwaj and Kalia (2020) also concluded that employees who have high work engagement will work well and carry out their work according to the rules, so that the work results provided will be maximized. Findings from Sanlioz, Sagbas, and Surucu (2022) also reveal that it is important for someone to have high engagement at work because, with high engagement, they will work seriously and complete their work, ultimately improving performance. Abdullahi, Raman, and Solarin (2021) also reveal that work engagement has a significant influence on performance. Susita *et al.* (2021) also found that work engagement has a significant and positive effect on improving employee performance. Based on this, the hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H5: Work engagement has a positive and significant effect on performance

Organizational support for performance through work engagement

Perceived organizational support can give rise to employee engagement and improve employee performance because employees feel that the organization appreciates their contribution, guarantees membership in the future, and provides the rights that employees expect. Employees feel indebted and obliged to reciprocate by showing enthusiasm when working. and enthusiasm when working so that employees can show better work results with their abilities to encourage increased employee performance. Meyers *et al.* (2019) state that work engagement can mediate the influence of organizational support on performance. Gemilang and Riana (2021) in their research also revealed that work engagement partially mediates the influence of organizational support on performance. Other findings from Susita *et al.* (2021) also revealed that organizational support has a positive and significant influence on performance, which is mediated by work engagement. Based on this, the hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H6: Work engagement mediates the effect of organizational support on performance

Organizational culture on performance through work engagement

Organizational culture is the main factor in achieving expected performance. Organizational culture carries values, norms, and behavior that can shape work patterns, where the better the pattern, the better the resulting performance. An organizational culture that is perceived to be in accordance with the individual characteristics of organizational members will have an impact on their deep involvement in their work, which will provide the expected work results. Abdullahi, Raman, and Solarin (2021) concluded in their research that work engagement felt by employees can provide encouragement for the existing organizational culture in creating expected performance. Michulek *et al.* (2023) also concluded that work engagement can partially mediate the influence of organizational culture on performance. Finally, findings from Makhmut, Armanu, & Kurniawati (2023) also state that organizational culture can better influence performance when there is work involvement in it carried out by employees. Based on this, the hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H7: Work engagement mediates the influence of organizational culture on performance

Organizational Support on Work Engagement Moderated by Age

Working age plays an important role in creating a person's work engagement; Robbins (2005) says that the older a person is, the higher their work engagement. However, looking at the aspect of organizational support, it is said that organizational support will be better provided to young employees to increase their work engagement, compared to older people, because older employees tend to have high work engagement. In this research, old age is categorized as a generation, and the hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H8: Young employee age moderates the effect of organizational support on work engagement

METHOD

Study Design. This research uses an explanatory research approach with a correlational method with the unit of analysis, namely, health workers at all Public Health Centers in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. This study considered all health workers as a population of 1132 health workers. To determine the sample for this study, the Slovin formula was used with a total sample of 154 health workers divided into 15 Public Health Center units in Kendari City, where the sample in each service unit was divided using a proportional random sampling technique. The data in this study were collected through a questionnaire that was distributed in two ways: directly and through an online questionnaire.

Measures. To collect data, each research variable was measured using certain indicators, where the performance variable was measured using two performance dimensions from Government Regulation Number 30 of 2019, which consisted of the employee performance target dimension and the work behavior dimension. Next, the organizational support variable was measured based on Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002), which consists of (1) justice, (2) superior support, (3) appreciation, and (4) working conditions. Organizational culture variables are measured based on the Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) from Cameron and Quinn (2011) which consists of (1) Dominant characteristics, (2) Organizational leadership, (3) Employee management, (4) Organizational glue, (5) Orientation strategic, and (6) Success criteria. Work engagement is measured using indicators from Schaufeli et al. (2002), which consist of (1) Vigor, (2) Dedication, and (3) Absorption. Finally, for the age variable, this research uses Generation Theory as a basis for measuring age with two categories: Generation X and Generation Y.

Analysis. The data collected in this research will be analyzed using structural equational modeling analysis via Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) Version 3. Variable data on an ordinal and nominal scale are presented in frequency and percentage form, whereas variable data on an interval scale are presented as mean and standard deviation. Relationship analysis was carried out using the path coefficient test

RESULT

In this research, the characteristics of the respondents were based on a descriptive analysis carried out on the respondents' answers based on the existing questionnaire. It can be explained that the characteristics of this research can be seen in table 1.

Based on the characteristics presented in Table 1, it can be seen that the majority of health workers at the Public Health Center are women (103 people, 67 %), while there are 51 men (33 %). Health workers are dominated by Generation Y, with 98 people (64 %). Based on this, it can be concluded that the majority of workers at Public Health Centers are dominated by workers who have high flexibility, mobility, and orientation towards success, have a high level of creativity in their work, and produce the expected performance. At the educational level of the respondents, the majority were bachelor's degrees with a total of 87 people or 56%, and the majority had a working period of ≥ 11 years, with 91 people or 59%. Thus, it can be concluded that the majority of health workers had worked in their field for a long time. and have a good understanding of how their agency supports them in work, the existing values and norms and behavior, their engagement in work, and the performance they can produce in carrying out their duties.

Table 1: Characteristics of Research Respondents

Category	Characteristics	Amount (People)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	51	33
	Female	103	67
Age	27-42 (Gen Y)	98	64
	43-58 (Gen X)	56	36
Education	Associate's degree	55	36
	Bachelor Degree	87	56
	Master's Degree	12	8
Work Period	1 - 5 Years	23	15
	6 - 10 Years	40	26
	≥ 11 Years	91	59

Structural Model Testing

The testing of the structural model or inner model is evaluated by looking at the R2 value of the latent variable using the Geisser Q Square test, and then looking at the magnitude of the structural path coefficient. The stability of the estimates of the structural path coefficients was evaluated using the t-test statistics obtained from the bootstrapping procedure. Inner model testing can be seen from the R-square of the similarities between the latent variables. The results of the R-squared calculation are shown in Table 2.

Based on the calculation results in the table above, the total coefficient of determination (Q2) was used to test the feasibility of the model. Q-Square measures how good the observation values produced by the model are, as well as the estimated parameters. To determine the Q-squared value, the following formula was used:

$$Q2 = 1 - (1-R12) * (1-R22)$$

The Q-square calculations using R-square data in the three models above can be performed as follows:

$$Q2 = 1 - (1- 0,636) * (1-0,525) \rightarrow Q2 = 0,827$$

A Q-square value of 0.827 was obtained based on the Q-square (Q2) calculation. This figure can be interpreted to mean that the research model can explain 82.7% of the contribution of the influence of the organizational support and organizational culture variables on work engagement and performance of 82.7%, so the model has been built to have predictive relevance value or a good level of prediction.

Table 2: R-Square Calculation Results

Variable	R Square
Performance	0.636
Work Engagement	0.525

Figure 2: Direct Effect Testing Model

Table 3: Recapitulation of Research Results

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
H1 Organizational Support -> Work Engagement	0.177	2.665	0.008
H2 Organizational Support -> Performance	0.192	2.990	0.003
H3 Organizational Culture -> Work Engagement	0.601	9.726	0.000
H4 Organizational Culture -> Performance	0.176	2.102	0.036
H5 Work Engagement -> Performance	0.527	7.735	0.000

Direct Effect Testing

Based on Figure 2 and also table 3 presented, it can be seen that each influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable has a positive influence. Based on the test results presented in table 3 related to H1, the path coefficient value is 0.177, this means that there is a positive influence between organizational support and work engagement. In addition, testing the significance of this variable has a t-statistical value of 2.665 (>1.96) with a p-value of 0.008 (<0.05), which means that there is a significant influence between organizational support and work engagement. Based on these results, it can be concluded that organizational support has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. This means that organizational support provided to organizational members is able to provide positive changes to the work engagement of organizational members. Thus, Hypothesis 1 can be accepted. The next test regarding the influence of organizational support on performance produces a path coefficient value of 0.192 and a t-statistic value of 2.990 (>1.96) with a p-value of 0.003 (<0.05), which means there is a significant influence between organizational support. on Performance. Thus, H2 can be accepted.

Testing the influence of organizational culture on work engagement produces a path coefficient value of 0.601 and a t-statistic value of 9.726 (>1.96) with a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), which means there is a significant influence of organizational support. on work engagement. Meanwhile, the influence of organizational culture on performance produces a path coefficient value of 0.176 and a t-statistic value of 2.102 (>1.96) with a P-value of 0.036 (<0.05), which means that there is a significant influence between organizational culture and performance. Based on these results, it can be concluded that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work engagement performance. This means that a good existing organizational culture will be able to provide positive changes in work engagement and the resulting performance. Based on this, proposed H3 and H4 can be accepted.

Finally, testing the influence of work engagement on performance produces a path coefficient value of 0.527 and a t-statistic value of 7.735 (>1.96) with a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), which means there is a significant influence of work engagement. on Performance. Based on these results, we can conclude that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on performance. This means that the work engagement of health workers encourages good performance. The direction of this influence is positive, which means that the better the work engagement, the better is the resulting performance. Based on this, H5 is accepted.

Table 4: Indirect Effect Testing

Mediation		Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values
H6	Organizational Support -> Work Engagement -> Performance	0.093	2.741	0.006
H7	Organizational Culture -> Work Engagement -> Performance	0.317	5.503	0.000

Table 5: Testing the Moderation Effect

Effect of Moderating Variables		Path Coefficient	P Values	Sig
Exogenous	Endogenous			
Age	Work Engagement	0.037	0.504	Not Sig.
Age*Organizational Support	Work Engagement	0.132	0.005	Sig

Mediation Testing

Based on the results of tests carried out on indirect effects using SmartPLS Ver, 3 analysis tools, the results are shown in Table 4. Based on Table 4, it can be explained that the mediation test carried out on H6 was found to have a path coefficient value of 0.093, a t-value of 2.741, and a p-value of 0.006 (<0.05), so it can be concluded that work engagement mediates the influence of organizational support on performance. On this basis, H 6 was declared acceptable. Furthermore, testing the indirect influence found that H7 had a path coefficient value of 0.317, a statistical t value of 5.503, and a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), so it could be concluded that work engagement mediates the influence of organizational culture on performance. Therefore, H7 was accepted.

Moderation Testing

The results of tests carried out on the effect of moderation to answer the hypotheses of this research are shown in Table 5. Based on Table 5, the results of the moderation test on H8 show that the direct influence of the age variable on work engagement has a coefficient value of 0.037 with a p-value of 0.504 ($p > \alpha = 0.05$), which shows an

insignificant effect. Furthermore, when testing the interaction model between age and organizational support on work engagement, it was found to have a path coefficient value of 0.132 with a p-value of 0.005 ($p < \alpha = 0.05$), which means that the effect is significant. Thus, it can be concluded that young age can moderate the influence of organizational support on work engagement. This can be interpreted as that the organizational support given to young health workers will strengthen the involvement or work engagement they have in their work. Thus, H8 was accepted.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study reveal that organizational culture makes the most dominant contribution to shaping the work engagement of health workers. These findings show that it is necessary for the Kendari City Public Health Center to maintain the process of creating existing values, norms, and behaviors because this can be well accepted by health workers. Organizational culture, in which the characteristics of good cooperation are formed, and good organizational leadership in creating appropriate rules, management of existing employees, and the orientation of work units are important points that form ties between the organization and its members, thus creating work engagement.

Regarding performance, this study reveals that organizational culture has little direct impact on shaping performance. From these findings, it can be seen that work engagement, which is formed from good organizational culture within the organization, can better support the process of improving performance. Therefore, it is important for organizations to create work engagement in their members so that work engagement will support the role of culture in creating performance.

Work engagement in this study has a significant meaning because it has a positive influence on improving performance. However, regarding the mediating role of organizational support, it was found that the role of work engagement is very small in supporting increased performance, whereas the role of direct influence is relatively greater. Therefore, it is best for future research to change the position of work engagement to be exogenous in relation to organizational support.

Organizational culture is an interesting exogenous variable because it directly has a large influence on creating work engagement behavior and supports this in achieving work results. This is an important finding for research in which the Public Health Center needs to pay more attention to aspects that can form a better organizational culture, which is useful for creating better working conditions that can be accepted by existing organizational members.

This study also reveals the role of young people in health workers in strengthening organizational support to create work engagement behavior. This is because young health workers or Generation Y workers still have a lower level of empowerment than older health workers. Older health workers tend to have better engagement with their work because they usually devote their entire career to their work units. The findings of this research illustrate that in efforts to provide organizational support, organizations need to focus on how to support workers who are at a young, productive age to increase their work engagement.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that organizational support can positively influence work engagement and performance. This can be interpreted to mean that the better the organizational support felt by employees, the better the work engagement behavior shown by health workers, as will their performance. Likewise, organizational culture, which from the results of the analysis, was found to play a dominant role in increasing the work engagement of health workers; thus, it is hoped that to maintain this, organizations should focus on establishing a good organizational culture to achieve organizational goals. On the other hand, organizational culture also has a good impact on improving performance. Work engagement, as a mediator of existing influences, was also found to have a good role in bridging the formation of health workers' performance through organizational efforts to create culture and provide support to its members. In this research, it was also found that young people in Generation Y are able to strengthen the influence of organizational support provided in shaping their work engagement, thus giving organizations the idea that they can focus on forms of support for this generation to get workers who can work better.

Organizational support in this research was still found to be not optimal in increasing work engagement and performance; therefore, organizations need to pay attention to this. Organizations need to focus on improving the aspects of leadership support provided, creating more appropriate and comfortable working conditions, and providing adequate facilities to support conducive working conditions. Faced with improvements in these aspects, organizational support can be even better in creating work behavior, employee engagement, and performance. Organizational culture was found to be the aspect that contributes most dominantly to creating work engagement behavior; to maintain this, organizations need to continue to pay attention to aspects that form the glue of the organization, such as cooperation between co-workers or superiors and determining success criteria that can be benchmarks for employees in carrying out their work.

Work engagement plays an important role in supporting organizational culture and improving health workers' performance. To increase work engagement behavior, organizations need to continue to increase employee enthusiasm for work and a sense of pride, which will lead to high dedication from employees to work even better. Regarding employee age, this research reveals that young age can strengthen the influence of the organizational support provided to create work engagement. Therefore, organizations need to focus on empowering employees who fall into Generation Y to optimize their work engagement because this generation is still classified as a highly productive worker.

This research also has several limitations, inc first of which is quantitative research with data that analyzes respondents in a one-time condition, which allows for changes in existing conditions due to the dynamics of individual characteristics that continue to change. Therefore, it is hoped that in the future, we can use data that are better able to cover this, such as time series data, so that the results can cover existing situational changes. Second, this research was limited to the scope of health services at the first level, where conditions will differ from advanced health service centers or other health service scopes. This may limit the generalizability of this study's findings. For this reason, it is hoped that future research can re-test this research model in a wider scope, such as hospitals or other health facilities, whether run by the government or

the private sector, so that generalization of the findings of this research can be developed. Third, in testing the mediating effect of work engagement on the influence of organizational support on performance, it was found to have a significant effect, but the effect was very small compared to the direct effect. Therefore, it is hoped that further research can examine the work engagement variable as an independent variable or examine its moderating role in strengthening organizational support in creating performance.

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